

Angelo Leogrande^{1*}°

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Turnover in the Service Sector in Europe

Between the second quarter of 2020 and the third quarter of 2022 it grew on an average of 83.24%

The Eurostat calculates the value of the turnover in the service sector. The indicator consists of an index number with a value of 100 in 2015. The data are four months.

Ranking of countries by turnover value in the service sector in the 3 quarter in 2022. Turkey is in the first place for turnover value in the service sector with a value equal to 859.1 units, followed by Hungary with a value equal to 230.7 units and Lithuania with a value of 226.2 units. In the middle of the standings there are Slovakia with an amount of 161 units, followed by Latvia with a value of 159.1 units and by Croatia with an amount of 158.7 units. Austria closes the ranking with an amount of 133.1 units, followed by Greece with a value of 127.8 units and by Italy with an amount of 124.5 units.

Ranking of countries by the percentage variation of turnover in the service sector between 2020-Q2 and 2022-Q3. Turkey is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of turnover in services with an amount equal to 368.94% equal to an amount of 675.4 units, followed by Spain with an amount of 80.39% equal to an amount of 66.8 units, Malta with an amount of 80.39% equal to an amount of 74.6 units. In the middle of the standings there are Greece with an amount of 63.43% equal to an amount of 49.6 units, followed by Estonia with an amount of 61.01% equal to a value of 65.3 units, followed by Luxembourg with an amount of 60.59% equal to an amount of 59.5 units. Slovakia closes the ranking with an amount of 44.52% equal to an amount of 49.6 units, followed by Germany with a value of 41.89% equal to a value of 42.1 units and from Finland with a value equal to 36% equal to a value of 36.4 units.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. Below is a clusterization using the K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. The analysis shows the presence of three Clusters as indicated below or:

- Cluster 1: Romania, Lithuania, Hungary, Poland, Bulgaria;
- Cluster 2: Czech Republic, Spain, Malta, Germany, Cyprus, Belgium, Finland, Austria, Portugal, Netherlands, Croatia, Italy, Greece, Denmark, Slovenia, Latvia, Slovakia, Luxembourg, Estonia;
- Cluster 3: Türkiye.

Below is an order of the Clusters or: $C3 = 859.1 > C1 = 219.9 > C2 = 157.7$. The geography of the profit deriving from the service sector highlights the dominance of Turkey, followed by the weights of Eastern Europe and the countries of Western and southern Europe.

Network analysis with the Euclidean distance. A Network Analysis is presented below using the Euclidean distance. A complex network structure and three simplified network structures is detected.

The complex network structure is composed as indicated below:

¹Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

- Croatia has a connection with Belgium equal to an amount of 0.21 units;
- Malta has a connection with Cyprus for a value of 0.24 units;
- Belgium has a connection with Croatia for a value of 0.21 units and with Cyprus for a value of 0.24 units;
- Cyprus has a connection with Malta for a value of 0.24 units and with the Czech Republic equal to a value of 0.2 units;
- The Czech Republic has a connection with Cyprus for a value of 0.2 units, with Germany equal to a value of 0.2 units and with Finland for a value of 0.22 units;
- Finland has a connection with Germany equal to an amount of 0.085 units and with the Czech Republic equal to an amount of 0.22 units;
- Germany has a connection with the Czech Republic equal to an amount of 0.2 units, and with Finland equal to an amount of 0.085 units.

There are also three structures with simplified networks or:

- Romania and Lithuania have a connection equal to a value of 0.22 units;
- Denmark and the Netherlands have a connection equal to a value of 0.21 units;
- Portugal and Italy have a connection for a value of 0.17 units.

Conclusions. The value of the turnover of the services has grown between the second quarter of 2020 and the third quarter of 2022 from an amount of 105.37 units up to a value of 193.09 units or a growth equal to an amount of 83.24% even to an amount of 87.72 units. This indicator shows that from 2015 to 2022 the turnover in the service sector grew by 93 points. In the data there is no trace of a reduction in the value of the turnover that is somehow attributable to the crisis by Covid 19 or the energy crisis. It follows that the service sector is waterproof compared to the adversities of the macro-economic cycle also induced by international political phenomena.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Ranking dei paesi per variazione percentuale del fatturato nei servizi							
Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per	Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per
1	<i>Türkiye</i>	675,9	368,94	14	<i>Luxembourg</i>	59,5	60,59
2	<i>Spain</i>	66,8	80,39	15	<i>Slovenia</i>	62,7	59,71
2	<i>Malta</i>	74,6	80,39	16	<i>Italy</i>	46,1	58,8
4	<i>Croatia</i>	70,3	79,52	17	<i>Hungary</i>	84,2	57,47
5	<i>Lithuania</i>	97,6	75,89	18	<i>Latvia</i>	56,9	55,68
6	<i>Belgium</i>	65,9	74,89	19	<i>Bulgaria</i>	67	55,01
7	<i>Cyprus</i>	69,5	74,17	20	<i>Czechia</i>	51,4	52,5
8	<i>Romania</i>	92,9	73,15	21	<i>Austria</i>	44	49,38
9	<i>Denmark</i>	71	69,68	22	<i>Netherlands</i>	51,4	47,9
10	<i>Poland</i>	85,4	69,54	23	<i>Slovakia</i>	49,6	44,52
11	<i>Portugal</i>	56,8	69,27	24	<i>Germany</i>	42,1	41,89
12	<i>Greece</i>	49,6	63,43	25	<i>Finland</i>	36,4	36
13	<i>Estonia</i>	65,3	62,01				

Rank	Country	2022-Q3	Rank	Country	2022-Q3
1	<i>Türkiye</i>	859,1	14	<i>Croatia</i>	158,7
2	<i>Hungary</i>	230,7	14	<i>Netherlands</i>	158,7
3	<i>Lithuania</i>	226,2	15	<i>Luxembourg</i>	157,7
4	<i>Romania</i>	219,9	16	<i>Belgium</i>	153,9
5	<i>Poland</i>	208,2	17	<i>Spain</i>	149,9
6	<i>Bulgaria</i>	188,8	18	<i>Czechia</i>	149,3
7	<i>Denmark</i>	172,9	19	<i>Germany</i>	142,6
8	<i>Estonia</i>	170,6	20	<i>Portugal</i>	138,8
9	<i>Slovenia</i>	167,7	21	<i>Finland</i>	137,5
10	<i>Malta</i>	167,4	22	<i>Austria</i>	133,1
11	<i>Cyprus</i>	163,2	23	<i>Greece</i>	127,8
12	<i>Slovakia</i>	161	24	<i>Italy</i>	124,5
13	<i>Latvia</i>	159,1			

